

Environmental Impact Assessment of Urban Waste Recycling Challenges: A Review of DPSIR for Life Cycle Assessment of Municipal Solid Waste Recycling Challenges in Greater Monrovia, Liberia

Maxwell Bigboyo Borbor

*Institute of Environment for Sustainable Development, College of Environmental Science and Engineering,
Tongji University, 1239 Siping Road, Shanghai 200092, PR China*

Suggested Citation

Borbor, M.B. (2024).
Environmental Impact Assessment
of Urban Waste Recycling
Challenges: A Review of DPSIR
for Life Cycle Assessment of
Municipal Solid Waste Recycling
Challenges in Greater Monrovia,
Liberia. *European Journal of
Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(3),
999-1019.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(3\).78](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(3).78)

Abstract:

This study evaluates the environmental impact of municipal solid waste management recycling probability in Greater Monrovia, using the Driver-Pressure-State-Impact-Response (DPSIR) framework and Life Cycle Assessment (LCA). Greater Monrovia generates approximately 236155 tons of recyclable waste annually, comprising biodegradable, plastics, paper, inert materials, and assorted waste. Inadequate infrastructure causes less waste collection, and most are openly dumped or burned, triggering severe environmental pollution. The LCA examines key impact categories, including global warming potential (GWP), water pollution, resource depletion, and human health impacts across four waste management scenarios. Scenario one (Landfill) identified significant emissions, contributing

to global warming (194.86 kg CO₂ eq), marine aquatic ecotoxicity (MAE) (2259578 kg 14-DB eq), and human toxicity (172.59 kg 14-DB eq). Scenario two (Anaerobic Digestion) illustrates lower impacts on human toxicity (237.83 kg 14-DB eq) and freshwater aquatic ecotoxicity (86.99 kg 14-DB eq), with moderate GWP (415.51 kg CO₂ eq). In Scenario three, (Open Burning) results are the highest GWP (444.03 kg CO₂ eq) and MAE (1426606.7 kg 14-DB eq), indicating substantial environmental and health risks. Scenario Four, a combined approach integrating landfill, anaerobic digestion, and open burning, optimizes the strengths and mitigates the weaknesses of each scenario, offering a balanced approach with reduced impacts across multiple categories.

Findings indicate Scenario Two has a relatively moderate environmental impact. Assumed as the most preferred scenario based on the waste management option due to low environmental effects, thereby recommended as the appropriate technology for the MSW recycling process in Greater Monrovia, ultimately reducing environmental impacts and improving resource recovery.

Keywords: *Municipal Solid Waste, DPSIR, LCA, Recycling, Monrovia.*

Introduction

Greater Monrovia is a district of the capital city Monrovia, in Liberia. It is faced with significant challenges in managing its solid waste due to

rapid urban growth, inadequate infrastructure, and limited resources. Traditional waste management practices of open dumping and burning continuously pose environmental risks to the growing population. However, there are

increasing global concerns about transitioning towards sustainable waste management strategies that focus on resource recovery and adapting circular economy principles.

Municipal Solid Waste Management (MSWM) is amongst the major challenges developing countries urban cities face nowadays (Marshall & Farahbakhsh, 2013). The generation of MSW (Sharma & Jain, 2020) has risen significantly due to growing urbanisation and population increased (D. M.-C. Chen, Bodirsky, Krueger, Mishra, & Popp, 2020). Nonetheless, disposal techniques and waste management services remain at a low pace (Guerrero, Maas, & Hogland, 2013).

The sustainable management of municipal solid waste (MSW) is essential for public health, environmental protection, and resource conservation (Awasthi et al., 2019). Uncollected waste congests drains and contaminates water supplies (Regassa, Sundaraa, & Seboka, 2011), creating breeding grounds for environmental hazards and threats to public health (Alam & Ahmade, 2013). Effluence of uncontrolled waste disposal, open-dumping, and burning hazardously pollute the air, water, and soil (Siddiqua, Hahladakis, & Al-Attiya, 2022). Subsequently, these wastes contain appreciable resources and energy that could be recovered for economic development (Kumar & Samadder, 2017). Integrated sustainable waste management systems accordingly manage urban municipalities and harness the resources entrenched in solid wastes.

Generally, solid waste management (SMW) is a substantial challenge in Monrovia, Liberia (Bundhoo, 2018), as in many Sub-Saharan African cities (Kubanza & Simatele, 2018). Rapid urbanization, economic expansion, and shifting consumer behaviours have all contributed to the generation of accompanying solid waste (Liu, Li, Gu, & Wang, 2019), which has exacerbated the uncontrolled waste management systems (Mensah, 2006). The management of increasing waste is further complicated by environmental, socio-economic, and health impacts (Marshall & Farahbakhsh, 2013), as well as the critical need for effective

application of recycling mechanisms (S. Khan, Anjum, Raza, Bazai, & Ihtisham, 2022).

Monrovia generates about 600 metric tons of waste daily, composed of approximately 65% organics, 15% plastics, 5% paper, 5% inert materials, and 10% assorted waste types (Wilson & Velis, 2015) (UNEP, 2015). The average household waste per capita generation in Monrovia is estimated at 0.76kg/capita/day (David, Wenchao, & Mmereki, 2020), and the main percentage of waste generated in Monrovia, Liberia was organic (40.20%) refuse and plastic (14.2%) (David, Wenchao, Johna, & Mmereki, 2019). A minimum portion of this waste is formally collected and disposed of properly at the solitary authorized dumpsite in Whein Town (David et al., 2019); the suburban area of Monrovia.

The rapid population growth (Ezeh, Kissling, & Singer, 2020) is overtaking the waste infrastructure of Monrovia's residential capacity which has increased over 70% since 1980 to more than one million inhabitants today (Amoak, Bruser, Antabe, Sano, & Luignaah, 2023; Hoffman, 2017). This speedy urbanization has overwhelmed the city's capacity for waste collection and disposal (Oteng-Ababio, Arguello, & Gabbay, 2013). With this intense growth in the municipal population (Fox, 2012), the solid waste management practices in Monrovia are composed of multiple critical components that include waste generation and composition, collection and transportation, treatment and disposal, and policy and regulatory framework (Bundhoo, 2018). The effectiveness of the city's waste management system depends profoundly on each of these components.

With the challenge in its waste management practices across its municipalities, like many Sub-Saharan African countries (Mabogunje, 1995), efforts have been made by non-governmental organizations (NGOs) with community-based organizations (CBOs) to mitigate the glitches faced with MSW regulations in Sub-Saharan cities such as Monrovia, in Liberia (Henry, Yongsheng, & Jun, 2006).

There has been many research conducted on solid waste management in Monrovia(David et al., 2020) from a broader perspective on MSW generation generically(Bundhoo, 2018). Without a systemic approach on assessing the resource components of the generated waste strenuously., attempts on many occasions have yield futile due to the issues of management irregularities(Ayeleru et al., 2020).

The paper focuses on waste management practices in the Greater Monrovia area through a review of the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of its MSW system. Using the Driver, Pressures, States, Impact, and Response (DPSIR) framework to evaluate the MSW approach(Godfrey et al., 2019; Ramos-Quintana et al., 2018). Understanding the trends of Drivers in these practices allows the projection of future waste volumes. Quantifying the flows of waste by the Pressures on the system. Attaining information on the current State of the urban environment. Measuring the Impacts of MSW pressures on the environment. And comparing alternative waste management systems and technologies to inform policy and investment Responses to mitigate waste impacts(Ehara et al., 2018; Kanwal, Zeng, & Li, 2022; Ramos-Quintana et al., 2018). Through evaluation of the LCA of MSW management of Greater Monrovia, with the DPSIR framework. Using drivers of developing countries' implementation systems and how efficient it would align with the achievements of global environmental impact in developed countries. In consonance with the Sustainable Development Goals(SDGs) pillars on, public health (SDG 3), environmental sustainability (SDG 6 & 13), and resource generation (SDG 11), that address issues related to fundamental mitigation of waste by 2030(Gasper, Shah, & Tankha, 2019; Wilson, 2007).

Despite only around 20-25% of generated waste being collected, the rest openly dumped on street corners and burned(Townsend, 2019). Waste collection services using dump trucks and disposal containers only extend across 30-40% of the municipal area(Innis & van Assche, 2022). Assessing the formation of the generation, collection, segregation, and disposal(Miezah,

Obiri-Danso, Kádár, Fei-Baffoe, & Mensah, 2015) processes that would lead to an active circular economy approach of the municipal waste management system(Ferronato et al., 2019) in Monrovia is of high importance as in developing nations(Gariba, 2011).

The research provides a systematic review of life cycle assessment of MSW drifts and consequences in Greater Monrovia. Covering the process from MSW generation to disposal. Quantifying the effects of existing waste management practices on the ecosystem and simulating alternative integrated systems that include resource recovery(Allegrini et al., 2014). Results would offer information and propositions to help the City of Monrovia mitigate supplementary social environmental waste management practices as other developing municipalities(Mmerek, Baldwin, & Li, 2016).

Municipal Solid Waste Management in Sub-Saharan African Countries

Municipal solid waste management continues to be a major environmental challenge(Mabogunje, 1995) throughout Sub-Saharan Africa(Ezeah & Roberts, 2014). In Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) cities, generation of MSW is increasing histrionically due to rapid urbanization and population increase(Serge Kubanza & Simatele, 2020). By 2025, the average amount of waste produced in SSA is projected to increase from 0.65 kg per capita per day in 2015 to 1.42 kg per capita per day(Kaza, Yao, Bhada-Tata, & Van Woerden, 2018). In 2015, only 20% of urban populations in SSA had access to regular solid waste collection, and less than 10% of MSW generated underwent material recovery(Sanjeevi & Shahabudeen, 2015). MSWM systems, however, have not been actively managing the rising volume of waste produced. Approximately 90% of MSW in SSA ends up in uncontrolled dumpsites or opened burning(Remigios, 2010) due to inadequate collection coverage and managed disposal, which results in up to 70% of garbage generated uncollected(Hoornweg & Bhada-Tata, 2012).

DPSIR of Municipal Solid Waste LCA in SSA

Life Cycle Assessment is an important component in shifting the management of MSW in Sub-Saharan African municipalities to a Circular Economy (CE) approach. The DPSIR is a pertinent framework to evaluate the social, economic, and environmental impact (Spang et al., 2019) of the different waste management systems and vividly identified transitional improved opportunities (Sundarakani, De Souza, Goh, Wagner, & Manikandan, 2010). The usage of DPSIR for LCA of MSW allows a comprehensive evaluation of the impact on the environment from all generated waste (Acquaye et al., 2018; Komakech, Sundberg, Jönsson, & Vinnerås, 2015). While the LCA provides a quantitative acumen amongst the different waste management systems to inform MSWM in SSA, there are some challenges and limitations often reveal by the application of the DPSIR (Juju et al., 2020; Mukoro, Gallego-Schmid, & Sharmina, 2021). Primarily, reliable waste quantifiable data and compositions pose the foremost challenge (Friedrich & Trois, 2011).

Several LCA studies conducted in African cities through the DPSIR suggest that the best course of action is to combine regulated disposal in landfills that are appropriately built, managed, and monitored with resource recovery through recycling and waste-to-energy integrated within a system (Acai & Amadi-Echendu, 2018; Cheng & Hu, 2010; Cleary, 2009). And recuperating in every regulatory aspect, which can significantly lessen the effects of resource depletion and global warming (Arafat, Jijakli, & Ahsan, 2015) when LCA is effectuated in SSA waste management systems (Laurent et al., 2014).

Results of LCA have identified the critical activities in the MSW life cycle that contribute to distinct impact categories in the African context (Miezah et al., 2015; Parrot, Sotamenou, & Dia, 2009). Transportation of waste results in emissions and the usage of fossil fuels (Hanif, 2018). Toxic emissions into the air, soil, and water result from careless disposal and burning of garbage (I. Khan, Chowdhury, & Techato, 2022; Mamady, 2016). Inadequate recycling

results in missed chances to recover resources and strains the extraction of new materials (Schulze, 2016). Greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions are caused by poor incineration and open disposal sites (Scarlat, Motola, Dallemand, Monforti-Ferrario, & Mofor, 2015). Water bodies and ecosystems become contaminated when solid waste and wastewater are not properly treated (Ligate et al., 2021; Wang & Dong, 2019). These are issues complicating the efficient practice of LCA in SSA cities (Das et al., 2019). Nonetheless, the DPSIR framework identified opportunities for its application to enhance sustainability and efficiency in waste management practices (Ayeleru et al., 2020; Couth & Trois, 2012; Margallo et al., 2019; Prosperi, Moragues-Faus, Sonnino, & Devereux, 2015).

MSWM West African Cities

Like many SSA cities, in West Africa, municipalities have seen an exponential increase in MSW generation (Godfrey et al., 2019; Soni, Das, & Kumar, 2023) in recent decades as a result of rapid urbanisation, population growth, and shifting consumption habits (Achankeng, 2003; Zorpas, 2020). West African cities' average daily garbage output per capita fluctuates from 0.39 to 1.92 kg (Ogwueleka, 2013). However, increasing MSW volumes have outpaced municipal capabilities (Soumahoro et al., 2021). Subsidiarity reforms have also transferred greater responsibility and decision-making (Asiedu-Ayeh, Guangyu, Obiora, & Asiedu-Ayeh, 2023; Kaza & Bhada-Tata, 2018; Soltani, Hewage, Reza, & Sadiq, 2015) on MSWM services to local municipal governments (Godfrey et al., 2019; Obirih-Opareh, 2002).

In 2013, majority of West African cities relied largely on insufficient open dumping and burning practices (Bundhoo, 2018), and spend less than 10% of their budget on MSW management (Oteng-Ababio et al., 2013). Even so, advancement of national policy agendas with DPSIR framework (Horan, 2020; Xue et al., 2021) is a catalyst for improvements in MSWM acceleration. For instance, aims for enhanced waste collection, controlled disposal, and

recycling are outlined in Ghana's 2010 National Environmental Sanitation Policy (Oteng-Ababio, Owusu-Sekyere, & Amoah, 2017). More environmentally approachable MSW methods are also required by Nigeria's 2016 National Policy on the Environment and National Environmental Regulations (Awodele, Adewoye, & Oparah, 2016; Ogunkan, 2022).

Most municipalities in the region do not have the necessary technical and human resources to implement the required framework for efficient MSWM strategies (Vardopoulos et al., 2021). For waste management planning, policy creation, indenture management, and technical design, local governments frequently lack specialized personnel (Babayemi & Dauda, 2009; Tsheleza, Nakin, Ndhleve, Kabiti, & Musampa, 2019). Infrastructure development and integrated MSWM strategy are hampered by these factors (Ferrari, Cerise, Gamberini, Rimini, & Lolli, 2016). Despite rules that encourage waste separation from its source and controlled disposal, residents are also unable to engage in indiscriminate dumping and burning due to lax regulatory enforcement and monitoring (Ezeah & Roberts, 2012). Additionally, cross-border dumping and burning are motivated by intra-regional disparities (Østby, Nordås, & Rød, 2009) in West African cities, thus undermining national progress (Baldé, Wang, & Kuehr, 2016). For instance, least developing nations like Mali and Niger have cities without proper disposal facilities (Bundhoo, 2018; Saidou & Aminou, 2015). Consequently, waste is dumped in public spaces and along highways. Collaborative measures through LCA approach (Komakech et al., 2015; Ogundipe & Jimoh, 2015) with DPSIR framework are needed to resolve such disparities in regional waste management (Cudjoe & Acquah, 2021).

Many unsuitable predetermined performance and mismanagement of MSWM resources (Chang, Rusu, & Kohler, 2021) are amongst consequences of prevalent exploitation in municipal solid waste departments in most West Africa local governments (Achankeng, 2004; Juju et al., 2020). Municipal solid waste management agreements are frequently awarded to politically connected institutions (Ahmed &

Ali, 2004) through preference as opposed to open bidding (Post, 2004). Subsequently, for dogmatic fortification and inducements to government managers (Awortwi, 2012), these hired institutions disregard implementing contractual service criteria with impunity (Nzeadibe & Anyadike, 2012).

Materials and Methods

Study Area

The Greater Monrovia district includes some of the city's surrounding communities with a high population. According to a projection of the 2022 Liberia Demographic and Health Survey (LDHS) conducted by the Liberian Institute of Statistics and Geo-Information Services (LISGIS), the Greater Monrovia area has a population of 161,891 people, approximately 36% of Monrovia's total population. The district hosts most of the country's commercial and trade activities and higher institutional learning facilities. This research used the simplified clustered formulation for calculation of Greater Monrovia population (ALERT, 2023; Elloitt III & Padhya) to determine the desired cluster sample size. Therefore, with a population of approximately 161,891 inhabitants within a considerable 4 clusters, a 95% confidence level, a margin of error of 5%, an average cluster sampling size of 40,473 individuals, and an intra-cluster correlation coefficient of 0.02, the research selected and analyzed three clusters from the 4 clusters to achieve a 95% confidence level with a 5% margin of error for estimating the characteristics of the municipal solid waste management system. The primary data was used to categorize the three clusters in the Greater Monrovia area into different zones such as Market waste, (shops, hotels, and restaurants), Residential waste, and Roadside waste (open dumping sites).

MSW Collection

Municipal waste collection in Greater Monrovia emphasizes the role of transfer stations and municipal trucks in consolidating and transporting waste efficiently. Individuals and companies gather waste and place it in garbage

bins, which are subsequently hauled by smaller vehicles or scavengers to collection areas or transfer stations. At these transfer stations, waste is transferred onto larger municipal trucks for transmission to waste treatment or disposal

facilities. This procedure guarantees the desire to efficiently consolidate the movement of waste through different stages, which involves residents, commercial institutions, and municipal authorities.

Figure 1. Municipal Solid Waste Collection Process

MSW Characterization

Municipal solid waste generation in Monrovia is a growing challenge that requires an integrated approach to management. Rapid urbanization, population increase, and commercial expansion have led to an increase in the dimensions of waste generated, draining the city's inadequate waste management resources and infrastructure. According to studies (UNEP, 2019), more than 60% of the 0.65 kg of waste generated per capita in Monrovia daily can be recycled if segregated properly. However, most households do not separate their waste, leading to mixed waste being sent to dumpsites and opened landfill. Effective waste disposal remains a key component of MSWM in the city. Which is leading to a significant increase in environmental pollution and land degradation. All categories' total waste volume accounts for 360189 tons of total waste collected in 2023 in the municipal

area(Karak, Bhagat, & Bhattacharyya, 2012). These distribution of waste volumes and percentages across different categories provide insights into the composition of waste sources and their relative contributions to the total waste volume. It provides quantities of diverse types of waste materials used for waste management and recycling initiatives.

MSW Recyclable Composition

The study collected data from three municipal solid waste generation clusters (Market, Residential, and Roadside) in Greater Monrovia, categorized into Organic, Plastic, Paper, PET (Polyethylene terephthalate), and Others (glass, metal, textile, leather). Of the annual MSW collected, a total of 236155 tonnes of recyclable waste are separated from the waste stream. The data showed that organic waste accounted for 41.69% plastic waste 32.28%, paper waste 11.22%, PET 8.57%, and Others at 6.24%.

Table 1. Recyclable Municipal Composition

Waste Category	Market Waste Volume(t)	Market Waste (%)	Residential Waste Volume(t)	Residential Waste (%)	Roadside Waste Volume (t)	Roadside Waste (%)	Total Waste Volume (t)	Total Waste (%)
Organic	55696	64.35	23680	47.53	19082	19.12	98458	41.69
Plastic	21955	25.37	18020	36.18	36260	36.33	76235	32.28
Paper	3312	3.83	2063	4.14	21123	21.18	26498	11.22
PET	2148	2.48	3700	7.43	14385	14.41	20233	8.57
Others	3438	3.97	2349	4.72	8944	8.96	14731	6.24
Total	86549	100	49812	100	99794	100	236155	100

Figure 2. a) Municipal waste sources and b) Recycleable waste composition in Greater Monrovia area

Figure 3. DPSIR of MSWM in Greater Monrovia

The methodological approach evaluates the application of DPSIR in MSWM using LCA in Greater Monrovia. The DPSIR-LCA model identifies the waste management's functional unit and conceptual structure, with varying system boundaries on urban waste-to-resources. The DPSIR framework is applied to MSWM using LCA to address the challenges of waste mismanagement and its impact on environmental sustainability (Tokpah et al., 2022). This model defines the waste management system from the point of waste generation to disposal, considering society's environmental impact.

The DPSIR framework is integrated with the LCA model to assess the environmental impact of MSW generation and recycling probability. This integration allows for a comprehensive understanding of the interactions between human activities and waste management systems. The LCA model, when combined with the DPSIR framework, provides a robust tool for evaluating the environmental implications of municipal solid waste management systems and provides a comprehensive understanding of resource recovery.

Life Cycle Assessment

Life Cycle Assessment evaluates the environmental impacts of all the waste from raw material extraction through materials processing and disposal or recycling. The Goal and Scope of LCA define the purpose of the assessment, the product system to be studied, and the boundaries of the stages of the product life cycle. Outlining the intended audience and the expected uses of the study.

Life Cycle Inventory Analysis (LCIA) uses data and quantified inputs and outputs for each process in the product's life cycle. The inputs include raw materials from generated waste, while outputs might include emissions to air,

water, and soil, as well as other environmental releases. The compilation of this inventory allows for a detailed account of all environmental management processes.

Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) evaluates the potential environmental impacts of the product's life cycle. Linking inventory data with specific environmental impact categories, including global warming potential, ozone layer depletion, water pollution, and resource depletion. To assess the significance of the potential environmental impacts from the product lifecycle.

Interpretation is the final phase of LCA involving the evaluation of the results of the inventory analysis and impact assessment to make informed decisions or recommendations. Aiming to identify significant issues based on the results of the LCI and LCIA.

Results

LCA Scenarios

Municipal solid waste management emphasizes the importance of utilizing a comprehensive method to deal with solid waste management systems. Based on the composition of waste in Greater Monrovia, four (4) different scenarios were designed to assess municipal solid waste recycling challenges. Monrovia deals with overflowed disposal at landfills due to a consistent surge in municipal waste. To challenge this, a multifaceted scenario is projected. Characterizing the identified projected composition of Monrovia's waste stream, focusing on the proportions of recyclables waste. These scenarios aim to identify the most sustainable and efficient methods for managing collected recyclables from waste streams.

Figure 4. Scenario design of MSW

Scenario One: Landfill

Landfill has emerged as a decisive approach to mitigating the adverse environmental impacts associated with managing municipal solid waste, predominantly in developing nations experiencing rapid urbanisation and population growth (Catlin, Leonhardt, Wang, & Manuel, 2021). In Scenario One (Table 2), it was assumed that the recyclable waste materials contained compositions, such as combustible (paper), non-combustible (other), plastic, polyethylene terephthalate (PET), and biodegradable (organic) waste from the general waste collected. It is assumed that recyclable waste is disposed of and managed without the recovery of biogas, resulting in significant environmental pollution and contamination of municipal disposed

collection sites. Consequently, recyclables that emit gas through landfilling have a substantial impact on the reduction of characterized Global warming potential (GWP100a) (kg CO₂-Eq 194.8646), Marine aquatic ecotoxicity (kg 1,4-DB-Eq 2259578), Freshwater aquatic ecotoxicity (6035.7015 kg 1,4-DB Eq), produced from landfilling have a direct impact to increase greenhouse gas. Abiotic depletion (kg Sb Eq 0.0005), Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels) (MJ 1834.8314) Ozone layer depletion (ODP) (kg CFC-11 Eq 1.21E-05), Human toxicity (kg 1,4-DB Eq 172.58803), Terrestrial ecotoxicity (kg-1,4-DB-eq-0.95385795), Photochemical oxidation (kg-C₂H₄-Eq-0.046222758), Acidification (kg SO₂-Eq-0.59155643), and Eutrophication (kg PO₄ Eq-0.78318062) have moderate to low impact.

Table 2. Emission of MSW Scenario on Landfill Impact Categories (Characterisation of LCA)

Impact category	Unit	Results
Abiotic depletion	kg Sb eq	0.0005
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels)	MJ	1834.8314
Global warming (GWP100a)	kg CO ₂ eq	194.8646

Ozone layer depletion (ODP)	kg CFC-11 eq	1.21E-05
Human toxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	172.58803
Freshwater aquatic ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	6035.7015
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	2259578
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	0.95385795
Photochemical oxidation	kg C2H4 eq	0.046222758
Acidification	kg SO2 eq	0.59155643
Eutrophication	kg PO4 eq	0.78318062

Table 3 Emission of MSW Scenario on Landfill Impact Categories (LCA Normalization)

Impact category	Unit	Total
Abiotic depletion	kg Sb eq	6.51E-12
Acidification	kg SO2 eq	1.84E-12
Eutrophication	kg PO4- eq	5.91E-12
Global warming (GWP100)	kg CO2 eq	4.35E-12
Ozone layer depletion (ODP)	kg CFC-11 eq	2.30E-14
Human toxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	1.78E-11
Freshwater aquatic ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	2.96E-09
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	4.32E-09
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	1.03E-11
Photochemical oxidation	kg C2H4 eq	4.81E-13

Scenario Two: Anaerobic Digestion

Anaerobic digestion of recyclable waste decomposes biodegradable matter without oxygen. This produces biogas, a mixture of methane (CH₄), carbon dioxide (CO₂), and digestate. This scenario proposes a solution for managing waste in highly populated urban areas with limited landfill space, thus lowering the demand on landfill capacity while generating renewable energy (Jin et al., 2021). The optimal utilization of anaerobic digestion for recyclable waste demands a wide-ranging evaluation of waste composition, process optimization, and market demand for digestate for soil alteration.

In Scenario Two, (Table 4) it was assumed that biodegradable waste would be separated, sorted, and managed through anaerobic digestion, as in waste categories such as recyclable refuse in the collected waste streams. An estimated 98458 tonnes of biodegradable waste were separated, and sorted, with combustible decomposable waste. The biodegradable content was used to ascertain the volume of GHG released from the

recycling process. The environmental impact of this scenario considered Global warming potential (GWP) (kg CO₂-Eq 1.05E-11) human and other ecotoxicity impacts show very low values suggesting minimal negative impact on human health and the environment. Abiotic depletions reflect low resource usage of anaerobic digestion. Ozone layer depletion (ODP) (kg CFC-11 Eq 9.18E-14), Acidification (kg SO₂-Eq 1.38E-11), Photochemical oxidation (kg C₂H₄ eq 2.52E-12), and Eutrophication (kg PO₄ eq 2.37E-11) are minimal impact category. Anaerobic digestion has low GHG emissions, making it a highly sustainable solution for waste management in terms of climate effect. Generating biogas as a renewable energy source, further lowering fossil fuel dependence and associated emissions. AD demonstrates great environmental efficiency with low consequences across several categories. The scenario minimizes global warming, making it an ideal solution for decreasing GHG emissions.

Table 4. Emission of MSW Scenario of Anaerobic Digestion Impact Categories (Characterization of LCA)

Impact category	Unit	Total
Abiotic depletion	kg Sb eq	1.5338472
Acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	3.3016502
Eutrophication	kg PO ₄ - eq	3.6422576
Global warming (GWP100)	kg CO ₂ eq	415.5052
Ozone layer depletion (ODP)	kg CFC-11 eq	2.22E-05
Human toxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	237.82529
Freshwater aquatic ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	86.989318
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	150399.9
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	4.0637157
Photochemical oxidation	kg C ₂ H ₄ eq	0.092806713

Table 5. Emission of MSW Scenario of Anaerobic Digestion Impact Categories (Normalization of LCA)

Impact category	Unit	Total
Abiotic depletion	kg Sb eq	9.80E-12
Acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	1.03E-11
Eutrophication	kg PO ₄ - eq	2.75E-11
Global warming (GWP100)	kg CO ₂ eq	1.00E-11
Ozone layer depletion (ODP)	kg CFC-11 eq	4.31E-14
Human toxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	4.16E-12
Freshwater aquatic ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	4.26E-11
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	2.93E-10
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	1.51E-11
Photochemical oxidation	kg C ₂ H ₄ eq	9.65E-13

Scenario Three: Open Burning

Open burning is typically for waste reduction and has the potential only to reduce landfill waste. And emits greenhouse gases, particulate matter (PM), volatile organic compounds (VOCs), and other air pollutants that contribute to air pollution and climate change which pose a high recycling environmental impact. Evaluating the environmental ramifications of open burning of MSW as a scenario for waste management impact assessments is vital for sustainable environmental waste management. Research have shown that opening burning minimizes the amount of waste transferred to landfills. For example, research revealed that waste-to-energy opening burning facilities higher greenhouse gas emissions considerably when compared to landfilling (Kourkoumpas et al., 2015).

The need for a more integrated approach to MSWM is imperative due to the threat posed by global climate change and the exhaustion of natural resources. Compared to the two

preceding waste management scenarios, open burning is a resilient waste management method that can handle an extensive range of waste categories and quantifiable rudiments in mixed solid waste. Scenario Three (Table 6) assumed that in Greater Monrovia, all waste products that could be classified—including non-combustible, combustible, plastic, biodegradable waste, and PET—would be combined and burned.

Consequently, the environmental impacts related to recyclable waste management could vary in different municipalities due to different technological approaches, and as such the environmental impact for Greater Monrovia are as follows, indicative of Climate change (GWP 100a) (kg CO₂-Eq 1.08E-11), Human toxicity (HTP) (kg 1,4-DB-Eq 1.30E-10) are notable areas of concern with potential adverse impact on climate and human health. Abiotic depletion, Ozone Layer Depletion, Photochemical Oxidation, Acidification, and Eutrophication, show minimal impacts, while Terrestrial

ecotoxicity (kg 1,4-DB-Eq), Freshwater aquatic ecotoxicity (kg 1,4-DB eq 1.79E-10) and Marine aquatic ecotoxicity (kg 1,4-DB eq) are high,

pointing significant environmental risk to aquatic ecosystem.

Table 6. Emission of MSW Scenario of Open Burning Impact Categories (Characterization of LCA)

Impact category	Unit	Total
Abiotic depletion	kg Sb eq	4.4558994
Acidification	kg SO2 eq	2.0028884
Eutrophication	kg PO4- eq	1.6222441
Global warming (GWP100)	kg CO2 eq	444.02654
Ozone layer depletion (ODP)	kg CFC-11 eq	1.92E-05
Human toxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	757.21408
Freshwater aquatic ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	429.85283
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	1426606.7
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	-2.6316718
Photochemical oxidation	kg C2H4 eq	0.11888458

Table 7. Emission of MSW Scenario of Open Burning Impact Categories (Normalization of LCA)

Impact category	Unit	Total
Abiotic depletion	kg Sb eq	2.85E-11
Acidification	kg SO2 eq	6.23E-12
Eutrophication	kg PO4- eq	1.23E-11
Global warming (GWP100)	kg CO2 eq	1.07E-11
Ozone layer depletion (ODP)	kg CFC-11 eq	3.73E-14
Human toxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	1.33E-11
Freshwater aquatic ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	2.11E-10
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	2.78E-09
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	-9.79E-12
Photochemical oxidation	kg C2H4 eq	1.24E-12

Scenario Four: Landfill, Anaerobic Digestion, Open burning

This scenario focuses on analyzing the previous recycling scenarios comparatively. In Scenario Four, it was assumed that biodegradable waste was separated, sorted, and managed through anaerobic digestion, similar to how other waste classifications were handled. Recycling ensures that plastics and PET are handled responsibly, being separated and sorted at recycling centers (Y. Chen et al., 2019). This prevents them from ending up in the soil, which can have negative effects on underground water. Combustible and non-combustible waste is collected, separated, and sorted at transfer stations. Thus, mitigating the significant effects that occur when Scenario three is utilized.

Given the preceding results, the fourth scenario optimizes the strengths of each method and was proposed to create a more balanced approach. The fourth scenario further incorporates the low abiotic depletion and acidification impacts from Landfill, the low human toxicity and aquatic ecotoxicity impact from Anaerobic Digestion, and the negative terrestrial ecotoxicity from Open burning to offset other impacts.

Considering Scenario Four (Table 8) findings for recycling MSW, the particular outcome categories that recycling activities directly impact, are mostly those on emissions, waste management, and resource consumption. Minimization of these waste saves energy use and lessens the requirement for raw material extraction all of which have a substantial impact on environmental impact factors.

Table 8. Comparative Emissions of MSW Impact Categories Based on LCA Characterization

Impact category	Unit	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3
Abiotic depletion	kg Sb eq	1.0193591	1.5338472	4.4558994
Acidification	kg SO2 eq	0.59155499	3.3016502	2.0028884
Eutrophication	kg PO4- eq	0.7819833	3.6422576	1.6222441
Global warming (GWP100)	kg CO2 eq	180.37388	415.5052	444.02654
Ozone layer depletion (ODP)	kg CFC-11 eq	1.18E-05	2.22E-05	1.92E-05
Human toxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	1016.7005	237.82529	757.21408
Freshwater aquatic ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	6041.8878	86.989318	429.85283
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	2214681.7	150399.9	1426606.7
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	2.7559314	4.0637157	-2.6316718
Photochemical oxidation	kg C2H4 eq	0.046222991	0.092806713	0.11888458

Table 9. Comparative Emissions of MSW Impact Categories Based on LCA Normalization

Impact category	Unit	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3
Abiotic depletion	kg Sb eq	6.51E-12	9.80E-12	2.85E-11
Acidification	kg SO2 eq	1.84E-12	1.03E-11	6.23E-12
Eutrophication	kg PO4- eq	5.91E-12	2.75E-11	1.23E-11
Global warming (GWP100)	kg CO2 eq	4.35E-12	1.00E-11	1.07E-11
Ozone layer depletion (ODP)	kg CFC-11 eq	2.30E-14	4.31E-14	3.73E-14
Human toxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	1.78E-11	4.16E-12	1.33E-11
Freshwater aquatic ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	2.96E-09	4.26E-11	2.11E-10
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	4.32E-09	2.93E-10	2.78E-09
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	1.03E-11	1.51E-11	-9.79E-12
Photochemical oxidation	kg C2H4 eq	4.81E-13	9.65E-13	1.24E-12

Figure 5. Life Cycle Environmental Impact of all Scenarios

In evaluating the municipal solid waste recycling scenarios for Greater Monrovia, the three scenarios - Landfill, Anaerobic digestion, and Open burning - were assessed across various environmental impact categories. Anaerobic Digestion consistently demonstrated lower impacts on Human Toxicity 23.39%, Freshwater Aquatic Ecotoxicity 1.43%, and Marine Aquatic Ecotoxicity 6.79% respectively. The AD scenario also has a moderate impact on GWP at 93.57% and Photochemical Oxidation at 78.06%. Nevertheless, it showed high values in categories like Acidification (100%) and Ozone Layer Depletion (100%). Opening burning, while effective in reducing Terrestrial Ecotoxicity (-64.76%), exhibited the highest impacts of Global Warming Potential (100%) and Abiotic Depletion (100%). Landfill has the lowest impact in Abiotic Depletion (22.87%) and Acidification (17.91%), but the highest in Human Toxicity (100%) and both Freshwater and Marine Aquatic Ecotoxicity (100%).

Discussion

For environmental challenges and potential solutions for MSW management in Greater Monrovia using the DPSIR framework and LCA. Four waste management-recycling scenarios were evaluated: Landfill, Anaerobic Digestion, Open Burning, and a combined approach. Landfill contributes significantly to global warming, marine aquatic ecotoxicity, and human toxicity. Anaerobic Digestion shows lower impacts on human toxicity and aquatic ecotoxicity, and potential for renewable energy generation, with moderate GWP. Open Burning has the highest environmental impacts, particularly in terms of global warming and aquatic ecotoxicity, making it the least sustainable option. The combined Scenario balances the strengths of each scenario, reducing impacts across multiple categories.

Amid challenges faced with waste management in Greater Monrovia, improvement is probable, particularly through renewable energy generation and an integrated waste management

approach. The application of DPSIR and LCA provides a robust analytical model for organizational sustainable waste management decisions.

Conclusion

The review on municipal solid waste management in Greater Monrovia uses the DPSIR framework and LCA to assess the environmental impacts of current waste management recycling probabilities. The findings reveal that most waste remains uncollected, leading to significant environmental pollution. The LCA results show that different waste management scenarios, including landfill, anaerobic digestion, open burning, and a combined method, have distinct environmental impacts. Anaerobic digestion is preferred for its lower impact on GWP and human toxicity. It further shows better performance in human toxicity and ecotoxicity categories, suggesting it is considered because the impacts are of primary concern in Greater Monrovia. The combined approach offers a balanced method to enhance waste management. Hence, strategic improvements in waste segregation, recycling, and sustainable waste management technologies are required to reduce environmental impacts and boost resource recovery. Furthermore, collaboration amongst government agencies, non-governmental organizations, and community-based organizations is crucial for transitioning towards a circular economy.

References

- Acai, J., & Amadi-Echendu, J. (2018). *Pavement infrastructure sustainability assessment: A systematic review*. Paper presented at the 2018 Portland International Conference on Management of Engineering and Technology (PICMET). <https://doi.org/10.23919/PICMET.2018.8481788>
- Achankeng, E. (2003). *Globalization, urbanization and municipal solid waste management in Africa*. Paper presented at the Proceedings of the African

Studies Association of Australasia and the Pacific 26th annual conference.

Achankeng, E. (2004). *Sustainability in municipal solid waste management in Bamenda and Yaounde, Cameroon*.

Acquaye, A., Ibn-Mohammed, T., Genovese, A., Afrifa, G. A., Yamoah, F. A., & Oppon, E. (2018). A quantitative model for environmentally sustainable supply chain performance measurement. *European journal of operational research*, 269(1), 188-205. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2017.10.057>

Ahmed, S. A., & Ali, M. (2004). Partnerships for solid waste management in developing countries: linking theories to realities. *Habitat International*, 28(3), 467-479. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0197-3975\(03\)00044-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0197-3975(03)00044-4)

Alam, P., & Ahmade, K. (2013). Impact of solid waste on health and the environment. *International Journal of Sustainable Development and Green Economics (IJS DGE)*, 2(1), 165-168.

Alert, W. (2023). Liberia. *Policy*.

Allegrini, E., Maresca, A., Olsson, M. E., Holtze, M. S., Boldrin, A., & Astrup, T. F. (2014). Quantification of the resource recovery potential of municipal solid waste incineration bottom ashes. *Waste Management*, 34(9), 1627-1636. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2014.05.003>

Amoak, D., Bruser, G., Antabe, R., Sano, Y., & Luignaah, I. (2023). Unequal access to improved water and sanitation in a post-conflict context of Liberia: Evidence from the Demographic and Health Survey. *PLOS Water*, 2(4), e0000050. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pwat.0000050>

Arafat, H. A., Jijakli, K., & Ahsan, A. (2015). Environmental performance and energy recovery potential of five processes for municipal solid waste treatment. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 105, 233-240. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2013.11.071>

Asiedu-Ayeh, E., Guangyu, C., Obiora, S. C., & Asiedu-Ayeh, L. O. (2023). Assessing social responsibility initiatives for public-private partnership success based on multi-criteria decision making: Evidence from municipal solid

waste management in Ghana. *Journal of Environmental Planning and Management*, 66(13), 2713-2738.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/09640568.2022.2082929>

Awasthi, M. K., Zhao, J., Soundari, P. G., Kumar, S., Chen, H., Awasthi, S. K., . . . Zhang, Z. (2019). Sustainable management of solid waste. In *Sustainable Resource Recovery and Zero Waste Approaches* (pp. 79-99): Elsevier.

Awodele, O., Adewoye, A. A., & Oparah, A. C. (2016). Assessment of medical waste management in seven hospitals in Lagos, Nigeria. *BMC public health*, 16(1), 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-016-2916-1>

Awortwi, N. (2012). Contracting out local government services to private agents: An analysis of contract design and service delivery performance in Ghana. *International Journal of Public Administration*, 35(13), 886-900. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01900692.2012.686033>

Ayeleru, O. O., Dlova, S., Akinribide, O. J., Ntuli, F., Kupolati, W. K., Marina, P. F., . . . Olubambi, P. A. (2020). Challenges of plastic waste generation and management in sub-Saharan Africa: A review. *Waste Management*, 110, 24-42. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2020.04.017>

Babayemi, J., & Dauda, K. (2009). Evaluation of solid waste generation, categories and disposal options in developing countries: a case study of Nigeria. *Journal of Applied Sciences and Environmental Management*, 13(3). <http://dx.doi.org/10.4314/jasem.v13i3.55370>

Baldé, C., Wang, F., & Kuehr, R. (2016). Transboundary movements of used and waste electronic and electrical equipment. *United Nations University, Vice Rectorate in Europe–Sustainable Cycles Programme (SCYCLE): Bonn, Germany*.

Bundhoo, Z. M. (2018). Solid waste management in least developed countries: current status and challenges faced. *Journal of Material Cycles and Waste Management*, 20, 1867-1877. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S10163-018-0728-3>

- Catlin, J. R., Leonhardt, J. M., Wang, Y., & Manuel, R. J. (2021). Landfill or recycle? Pro-environmental receptacle labeling increases recycling contamination. *Journal of consumer psychology*, 31(4), 765-772. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jcpy.1216>
- Chang, Z., Rusu, V., & Kohler, J. C. (2021). The Global Fund: why anti-corruption, transparency and accountability matter. *Globalization and Health*, 17(1), 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12992-021-00753-w>
- Chen, D. M.-C., Bodirsky, B. L., Krueger, T., Mishra, A., & Popp, A. (2020). The world's growing municipal solid waste: trends and impacts. *Environmental Research Letters*, 15(7), 074021. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ab8659>
- Chen, Y., Cui, Z., Cui, X., Liu, W., Wang, X., Li, X., & Li, S. (2019). Life cycle assessment of end-of-life treatments of waste plastics in China. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 146, 348-357. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2019.03.011>
- Cheng, H., & Hu, Y. (2010). Municipal solid waste (MSW) as a renewable source of energy: Current and future practices in China. *Bioresourcetechnology*, 101(11), 3816-3824. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2010.01.040>
- Cleary, J. (2009). Life cycle assessments of municipal solid waste management systems: A comparative analysis of selected peer-reviewed literature. *Environment international*, 35(8), 1256-1266. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2009.07.009>
- Couth, R., & Trois, C. (2012). Sustainable waste management in Africa through CDM projects. *Waste Management*, 32(11), 2115-2125. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2012.02.022>
- Cudjoe, D., & Acquah, P. M. (2021). Environmental impact analysis of municipal solid waste incineration in African countries. *Chemosphere*, 265, 129186. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2020.129186>
- Das, S., Lee, S.-H., Kumar, P., Kim, K.-H., Lee, S. S., & Bhattacharya, S. S. (2019). Solid waste management: Scope and the challenge of sustainability. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 228, 658-678. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.04.323>
- David, V. E., Wenchao, J., & Mmereki, D. (2020). Household solid waste management in Monrovia, Liberia: Influencing factors, characteristics, and management solutions. *The Journal of Solid Waste Technology and Management*, 46(1), 77-86. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5276/JSWTM/2020.77>
- David, V. E., Wenchao, J., Johna, Y., & Mmereki, D. (2019). Solid waste management in Monrovia, Liberia: Implications for sustainable development. *The Journal of Solid Waste Technology and Management*, 45(1), 102-110. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5276/JSWTM.2019.102>
- Ehara, M., Hyakumura, K., Kurosawa, K., Araya, K., Sokh, H., & Kohsaka, R. (2018). Addressing maladaptive coping strategies of local communities to changes in ecosystem service provisions using the DPSIR framework. *Ecological Economics*, 149, 226-238. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2018.03.008>
- Elloitt III, S. N., & Padhya, H. J. A Strategic Proposal For Post War Transition Of Monrovia City To Sustainable Development: Republic Of Liberia.
- Ezeah, C., & Roberts, C. L. (2012). Analysis of barriers and success factors affecting the adoption of sustainable management of municipal solid waste in Nigeria. *Journal of environmental management*, 103, 9-14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2012.02.027>
- Ezeah, C., & Roberts, C. L. (2014). Waste governance agenda in Nigerian cities: A comparative analysis. *Habitat International*, 41, 121-128. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.habitatint.2013.07.007>
- Ezeh, A., Kissling, F., & Singer, P. (2020). Why sub-Saharan Africa might exceed its projected population size by 2100. *The Lancet*, 396(10258),

1131-1133. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(20\)31522-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(20)31522-1)

Ferrari, K., Cerise, S., Gamberini, R., Rimini, B., & Lolli, F. (2016). An international partnership for the sustainable development of municipal solid waste management in Guinea-Bissau, West Africa. *XXI Summer School "Francesco Turco"—industrial systems engineering*, 113-117.

Ferronato, N., Rada, E. C., Portillo, M. A. G., Cioca, L. I., Ragazzi, M., & Torretta, V. (2019). Introduction of the circular economy within developing regions: A comparative analysis of advantages and opportunities for waste valorization. *Journal of environmental management*, 230, 366-378. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2018.09.095>

Fox, S. (2012). Urbanization as a global historical process: Theory and evidence from sub-Saharan Africa. *Population and development review*, 38(2), 285-310. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1728-4457.2012.00493.x>

Friedrich, E., & Trois, C. (2011). Quantification of greenhouse gas emissions from waste management processes for municipalities—A comparative review focusing on Africa. *Waste Management*, 31(7), 1585-1596. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2011.02.028>

Gariba, E. B. (2011). Post-conflict development in Liberia: Governance, security, capacity building and a developmental approach. *African Journal on Conflict Resolution*, 11(2), 105-132. <https://doi.org/10.4314/AJCR.V11I2.69835>

Gasper, D., Shah, A., & Tankha, S. (2019). The framing of sustainable consumption and production in SDG 12. *Global Policy*, 10, 83-95. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1758-5899.12592>

Godfrey, L., Ahmed, M. T., Gebremedhin, K. G., Katima, J. H., Oelofse, S., Osibanjo, O., . . . Yonli, A. H. (2019). Solid waste management in Africa: Governance failure or development opportunity. *Regional development in Africa*, 235. <https://doi.org/10.5772/INTECHOPEN.86974>

Guerrero, L. A., Maas, G., & Hogland, W. (2013). Solid waste management challenges for cities in developing countries. *Waste Management*,

33(1), 220-232. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2012.09.008>

Hanif, I. (2018). Impact of economic growth, nonrenewable and renewable energy consumption, and urbanization on carbon emissions in Sub-Saharan Africa. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 25(15), 15057-15067. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-018-1753-4>

Henry, R. K., Yongsheng, Z., & Jun, D. (2006). Municipal solid waste management challenges in developing countries—Kenyan case study. *Waste Management*, 26(1), 92-100. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2005.03.007>

Hoffman, D. (2017). *Monrovia modern: Urban form and political imagination in Liberia*: Duke University Press.

Hoornweg, D., & Bhada-Tata, P. (2012). What a waste: a global review of solid waste management.

Horan, D. (2020). National baselines for integrated implementation of an environmental sustainable development goal assessed in a new integrated SDG index. *Sustainability*, 12(17), 6955. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12176955>

Innis, P. G., & van Assche, K. (2022). The interplay of riskscape and objects in unplanned settlements in Monrovia. *Geoforum*, 136, 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2022.07.015>

Jin, C., Sun, S., Yang, D., Sheng, W., Ma, Y., He, W., & Li, G. (2021). Anaerobic digestion: An alternative resource treatment option for food waste in China. *Science of the Total Environment*, 779, 146397. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.146397>

Juju, D., Baffoe, G., Dam Lam, R., Karanja, A., Naidoo, M., Ahmed, A., . . . Takeuchi, K. (2020). Sustainability challenges in sub-Saharan Africa in the context of the sustainable development goals (SDGs). *Sustainability Challenges in Sub-Saharan Africa I: Continental Perspectives and Insights from Western and Central Africa*, 3-50. http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-4458-3_1

- Kanwal, Q., Zeng, X., & Li, J. (2022). Drivers-pressures-state-impact-response framework of hazardous waste management in China. *Critical Reviews in Environmental Science and Technology*, 52(16), 2930-2961. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10643389.2021.1902225>
- Karak, T., Bhagat, R., & Bhattacharyya, P. (2012). Municipal solid waste generation, composition, and management: the world scenario. *Critical Reviews in Environmental Science and Technology*, 42(15), 1509-1630. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10643389.2011.569871>
- Kaza, S., & Bhada-Tata, P. (2018). Decision maker's guides for solid waste management technologies.
- Kaza, S., Yao, L., Bhada-Tata, P., & Van Woerden, F. (2018). *What a waste 2.0: a global snapshot of solid waste management to 2050*: World Bank Publications.
- Khan, I., Chowdhury, S., & Techato, K. (2022). Waste to energy in developing countries—a rapid review: opportunities, challenges, and policies in selected countries of sub-saharan Africa and south asia towards sustainability. *Sustainability*, 14(7), 3740. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14073740>
- Khan, S., Anjum, R., Raza, S. T., Bazai, N. A., & Ihtisham, M. (2022). Technologies for municipal solid waste management: Current status, challenges, and future perspectives. *Chemosphere*, 288, 132403. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2021.132403>
- Komakech, A. J., Sundberg, C., Jönsson, H., & Vinnerås, B. (2015). Life cycle assessment of biodegradable waste treatment systems for sub-Saharan African cities. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 99, 100-110. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2015.03.006>
- Kourkoumpas, D.-S., Karellas, S., Kouloumoundras, S., Koufodimos, G., Grammelis, P., & Kakaras, E. (2015). Comparison of waste-to-energy processes by means of life cycle analysis principles regarding the global warming potential impact: applied case studies in Greece, France and Germany. *Waste and biomass valorization*, 6, 605-621. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s12649-015-9367-2>
- Kubanza, N. S., & Simatele, D. (2018). Sustainable solid waste management in sub-Saharan African cities: application of system thinking and system dynamic as methodological imperatives in Kinshasa, the Democratic Republic of Congo. *Local Environment*, 23(2), 220-238. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13549839.2017.1399996>
- Kumar, A., & Samadder, S. R. (2017). A review on technological options of waste to energy for effective management of municipal solid waste. *Waste Management*, 69, 407-422. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2017.08.046>
- Laurent, A., Clavreul, J., Bernstad, A., Bakas, I., Niero, M., Gentil, E., . . . Hauschild, M. Z. (2014). Review of LCA studies of solid waste management systems—Part II: Methodological guidance for a better practice. *Waste Management*, 34(3), 589-606. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2013.12.004>
- Ligate, F., Ijumulana, J., Ahmad, A., Kimambo, V., Irunde, R., Mtamba, J. O., . . . Bhattacharya, P. (2021). Groundwater resources in the East African Rift Valley: Understanding the geogenic contamination and water quality challenges in Tanzania. *Scientific African*, 13, e00831. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sciaf.2021.e00831>
- Liu, J., Li, Q., Gu, W., & Wang, C. (2019). The impact of consumption patterns on the generation of municipal solid waste in China: Evidences from provincial data. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 16(10), 1717. <https://doi.org/10.3390%2Fijerph16101717>
- Mabogunje, A. L. (1995). The environmental challenges in sub-Saharan Africa. *Environment: Science and Policy for Sustainable Development*, 37(4), 4-10. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00139157.1995.9929233>
- Mamady, K. (2016). Factors influencing attitude, safety behavior, and knowledge regarding

household waste management in Guinea: a cross-sectional study. *Journal of environmental and public health*, 2016. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2016/9305768>

Margallo, M., Ziegler-Rodriguez, K., Vázquez-Rowe, I., Aldaco, R., Irabien, Á., & Kahhat, R. (2019). Enhancing waste management strategies in Latin America under a holistic environmental assessment perspective: A review for policy support. *Science of the Total Environment*, 689, 1255-1275. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.06.393>

Marshall, R. E., & Farahbakhsh, K. (2013). Systems approaches to integrated solid waste management in developing countries. *Waste Management*, 33(4), 988-1003. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2012.12.023>

Mensah, A. (2006). People and their waste in an emergency context: the case of Monrovia, Liberia. *Habitat International*, 30(4), 754-768. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.habitatint.2005.09.002>

Miezah, K., Obiri-Danso, K., Kádár, Z., Fei-Baffoe, B., & Mensah, M. Y. (2015). Municipal solid waste characterization and quantification as a measure towards effective waste management in Ghana. *Waste Management*, 46, 15-27. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2015.09.009>

Mmereki, D., Baldwin, A., & Li, B. (2016). A comparative analysis of solid waste management in developed, developing and lesser developed countries. *Environmental Technology Reviews*, 5(1), 120-141. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21622515.2016.1259357>

Mukoro, V., Gallego-Schmid, A., & Sharmina, M. (2021). Life cycle assessment of renewable energy in Africa. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 28, 1314-1332. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2021.08.006>

Nzeadibe, T. C., & Anyadike, R. N. (2012). Social participation in city governance and urban livelihoods: Constraints to the informal recycling economy in Aba, Nigeria. *City, Culture and Society*, 3(4), 313-325. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ccs.2012.10.001>

Obirih-Opareh, N. (2002). *Solid waste collection in Accra: The impact of decentralisation and privatisation on the practice and performance of service delivery*: AGIDS.

Ogundipe, F., & Jimoh, O. D. (2015). Life cycle assessment of municipal solid waste management in Minna, Niger State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Environmental Research*, 9(4), 1305-1314.

Ogunkan, D. V. (2022). Achieving sustainable environmental governance in Nigeria: A review for policy consideration. *Urban Governance*, 2(1), 212-220. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ugj.2022.04.004>

Ogwueleka, T. C. (2013). Survey of household waste composition and quantities in Abuja, Nigeria. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 77, 52-60. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2013.05.011>

Østby, G., Nordås, R., & Rød, J. K. (2009). Regional inequalities and civil conflict in Sub-Saharan Africa. *International Studies Quarterly*, 53(2), 301-324. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2478.2009.00535.x>

Oteng-Ababio, M., Arguello, J. E. M., & Gabbay, O. (2013). Solid waste management in African cities: Sorting the facts from the fads in Accra, Ghana. *Habitat International*, 39, 96-104. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.habitatint.2012.10.010>

Oteng-Ababio, M., Owusu-Sekyere, E., & Amoah, S. T. (2017). Thinking globally, acting locally: formalizing informal solid waste management practices in Ghana. *Journal of Developing Societies*, 33(1), 75-98. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/0169796X17694517>

Parrot, L., Sotamenou, J., & Dia, B. K. (2009). Municipal solid waste management in Africa: Strategies and livelihoods in Yaoundé, Cameroon. *Waste Management*, 29(2), 986-995. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2008.05.005>

Post, J. (2004). Evolving partnerships in the collection of urban solid waste in the developing world. In *Solid Waste Management and Recycling*:

Actors, Partnerships and Policies in Hyderabad, India and Nairobi, Kenya (pp. 21-36): Springer.

Prosperi, P., Moragues-Faus, A., Sonnino, R., & Devereux, C. (2015). Measuring progress towards sustainable food cities: Sustainability and food security indicators. *Report of the ESRC financed Project "Enhancing the Impact of Sustainable Urban Food Strategies"*.

Ramos-Quintana, F., Ortíz-Hernández, M. L., Sánchez-Salinas, E., Úrsula-Vázquez, E., Guerrero, J. A., & Zamorano, M. (2018). Quantitative-qualitative assessments of environmental causal networks to support the DPSIR framework in the decision-making process. *Environmental Impact Assessment Review*, 69, 42-60. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eiar.2017.11.004>

Regassa, N., Sundaraa, R. D., & Seboka, B. B. (2011). Challenges and opportunities in municipal solid waste management: The case of Addis Ababa city, central Ethiopia. *Journal of human ecology*, 33(3), 179-190. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09709274.2011.11906358>

Remigios, M. V. (2010). An overview of the management practices at solid waste disposal sites in African cities and towns. *Journal of sustainable development in Africa*, 12(7), 233-239.

Saidou, H., & Aminou, S. (2015). Solid waste management in the town of Maradi in Niger Republic. *Journal of Environmental Protection*, 6(04), 359. <https://doi.org/10.4236/JEP.2015.64036>

Sanjeevi, V., & Shahabudeen, P. (2015). Development of performance indicators for municipal solid waste management (PIMS): A review. *Waste Management & Research*, 33(12), 1052-1065. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0734242x15607428>

Scarlat, N., Motola, V., Dallemand, J. F., Monforti-Ferrario, F., & Mofor, L. (2015). Evaluation of energy potential of municipal solid waste from African urban areas. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 50, 1269-1286. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2015.05.067>

Schulze, G. (2016). Growth within: A circular economy vision for a competitive Europe. *Ellen*

MacArthur Foundation and the McKinsey Center for Business and Environment, 1-22.

Serge Kubanza, N., & Simatele, M. D. (2020). Sustainable solid waste management in developing countries: a study of institutional strengthening for solid waste management in Johannesburg, South Africa. *Journal of Environmental Planning and Management*, 63(2), 175-188.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/09640568.2019.1576510>

Sharma, K. D., & Jain, S. (2020). Municipal solid waste generation, composition, and management: the global scenario. *Social Responsibility Journal*, 16(6), 917-948. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/SRJ-06-2019-0210>

Siddiqua, A., Hahladakis, J. N., & Al-Attiya, W. A. K. (2022). An overview of the environmental pollution and health effects associated with waste landfilling and open dumping. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 29(39), 58514-58536. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-022-21578-z>

Soltani, A., Hewage, K., Reza, B., & Sadiq, R. (2015). Multiple stakeholders in multi-criteria decision-making in the context of municipal solid waste management: a review. *Waste Management*, 35, 318-328. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2014.09.010>

Soni, A., Das, P. K., & Kumar, P. (2023). A review on the municipal solid waste management status, challenges and potential for the future Indian cities. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 25(12), 13755-13803. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10668-022-02688-7>

Soumahoro, N. S., Kouassi, N. g. L. B., Yao, K. M., Kwa-Koffi, E. K., Kouassi, A. M., & Trokourey, A. (2021). Impact of municipal solid waste dumpsites on trace metal contamination levels in the surrounding area: A case study in West Africa, Abidjan, Cote d'Ivoire. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 28, 30425-30435. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11356-021-13987-3>

- Spang, E. S., Moreno, L. C., Pace, S. A., Achmon, Y., Donis-Gonzalez, I., Gosliner, W. A., . . . Winans, K. S. (2019). Food loss and waste: measurement, drivers, and solutions. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, 44, 117-156. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1146/annurev-environ-101718-033228>
- Sundarakani, B., De Souza, R., Goh, M., Wagner, S. M., & Manikandan, S. (2010). Modeling carbon footprints across the supply chain. *International journal of production economics*, 128(1), 43-50. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2010.01.018>
- Tokpah, D. P., Aslanova, F., Dennis, O. G., Geninyan, N. R., George, A. G., Quoigoah, M. P., & Mason, M. N. (2022). An evaluation of solid waste management in Monrovia (Liberia).
- Townsend, R. E. (2019). *Leadership strategies for reducing operational costs in waste management businesses in Liberia*. Walden University,
- Tsheleza, V., Nakin, M. D., Ndhleve, S., Kabit, H. M., & Musampa, C. M. (2019). Vulnerability of growing cities to solid waste-related environmental hazards: The case of Mthatha, South Africa. *Jamba: Journal of Disaster Risk Studies*, 11(1), 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.4102/jamba.v11i1.632>
- Vardopoulos, I., Konstantopoulos, I., Zorpas, A. A., Limousy, L., Bennici, S., Inglezakis, V. J., & Voukkali, I. (2021). Sustainable metropolitan areas perspectives through assessment of the existing waste management strategies. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 28, 24305-24320. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-020-07930-1>
- Wang, J., & Dong, K. (2019). What drives environmental degradation? Evidence from 14 Sub-Saharan African countries. *Science of the Total Environment*, 656, 165-173. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.11.354>
- Wilson, D. C. (2007). Development drivers for waste management. *Waste Management & Research*, 25(3), 198-207. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/0734242X07079149>
- Wilson, D. C., & Velis, C. A. (2015). Waste management—still a global challenge in the 21st century: An evidence-based call for action. In (Vol. 33, pp. 1049-1051): SAGE Publications Sage UK: London, England.
- Xue, B., Liu, B., Yang, Q., Sun, X., Wang, W., & Li, L. (2021). Formalizing an evaluation-prediction based roadmap towards urban sustainability: A case study of Chenzhou, China. *Habitat International*, 112, 102376. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.habitatint.2021.102376>
- Zorpas, A. A. (2020). Strategy development in the framework of waste management. *Science of the Total Environment*, 716, 137088. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.137088>